

Analysis for Customer Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction Lazada Company as Intervening during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract:- This study explains the influence of Lazada's customer loyalty and satisfaction during a pandemic. This research was conducted virtually from February 2021 to June 2022 with 80 respondents using a purposive sampling technique. This research used four variables of brand image, customer experience, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The data in this study were obtained from primary sources using a questionnaire distributed online via the Google form and measured with a Likert scale. Testing the research hypothesis was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) based Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach. The results of this study, namely the results of hypothesis testing using smartPLS 4.0 in this study indicate that consumer customer experience and customer satisfaction in using Lazada products have a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty. But the brand image shows that there is a positive influence but not significant. This proves that the customer experience in this study when using Lazada products has a significant role in their satisfaction in using Lazada. Customer satisfaction can either improve or increase customer loyalty, so companies need to maintain a good experience for customers and this factor becomes one of the factors that strengthen customer loyalty to these products. Theoretical implications of this research are the implications of this research, namely that it is expected to be able to carry out both studies, namely qualitative and quantitative to provide more in-depth research results and more effective suggestions, using variables that are not used in the pre-survey table and further research can be carried out on e- other commerce or in other business sectors, because with different objects it is possible to produce different conclusions. The practical implication of this research is that Lazada companies still have to pay attention to changing times and have to maintain the existence of customers.

Keywords:- Loyalty, customer satisfaction, brand image, Lazada, Covid-19 Pandemic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's technology makes it easier for various activities to feel lighter and faster. One of them is in transacting using an online shop to meet needs. Utilization and use of internet technology is expected to provide great benefits to the competitive business world. Companies that are able to compete in this competition are companies that are able to implement technology and information into their companies. One type of technology implementation in terms of increasing business competition and selling products is to use electronic commerce (e-commerce) to market various kinds of products or services, both in physical and digital forms. The basic idea and benefits of e-commerce in increasing attractiveness to customers and increasing company competitiveness. In 2019 the Covid-19 pandemic occurred and e-commerce became very popular for the community.

Based on the increase or decrease between e-commerce companies in Indonesia that compete from year to year, there are 10 rankings sorted by the highest number of visitors. in 2017 Lazada is E-Commerce with the largest revenue, but until 2021, Lazada is always in 4th position, and always below Tokopedia, Bukalapak, and Shopee. With these results it is suspected that there is an influence between customer experience and brand image on customer loyalty at PT Lazada Indonesia. Based on the number of Lazada user transactions from 2019 to 2021, it shows that there has been a significant decrease from 2019 to 2021 in the number of Lazada application users. The problem in this study is that Lazada has experienced a decrease in ranking under other e-commerce which has resulted in a reduced number of visitors on the Lazada website. The same thing also happened with the increasing number of e-commerce users in Indonesia, regarding the increase in the number of current e-commerce users, not making Lazada the main e-commerce destination for customers. Customers still have other options to do online shopping and are also suspected of reducing the level of loyalty from Lazada customers. Based on the above, the purpose of this research is to analyze customer loyalty and customer satisfaction of Lazada companies during the Covid-19 pandemic.

II. HYPOTHESIS AND METHODS

A. The influence of customer experience on customer satisfaction

Hendra (2016) says that customer experience has a significant positive influence on customer satisfaction. Dewi and Hasibuan. (2016) have results where partially and simultaneously customer experience (Sense, Feel, Think, Act and Relate) has an effect on customer satisfaction.

H1: There is a significant influence of customer experience on customer satisfaction

B. Effect of brand image on customer satisfaction

Setyowati (2017) states that, there is a significant positive effect of brand image on customer satisfaction so that it can be said that a strong or attached brand image can increase customer satisfaction. Santoso (2016) also stated that brand image has a positive effect on customer satisfaction. The nature of the positive influence is significant.

- H2: There is a significant positive influence of brand image on customer satisfaction

C. The Effect of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

Orel & Kara (2018) state that, there is an influence from SCS services or online shopping that has a positive and significant effect on loyalty through the customer satisfaction channel. Sembiring (2014) also states that

A. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender (Gender)

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Women	38	48%
Male	42	52%
Total	80	100%

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

Source: processing data (2022)

Based on Table 1. shows that the characteristics of the respondents obtained based on gender, namely as many as 52.00% (52 respondents) were male, then 48.00% (48 respondents)

B. Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Age	Number of Respondents	Percentage
≤ 25 years	18	23.00%
26 - 30 years	38	48.00%
31 ≥ years	24	29.00%
Total	80	100%

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents by Age

Source: processing data (2022)

Based on Table 2 shows that 23% (18 respondents) were aged ≤ 25 years, 48% (38 respondents) were aged 26 to 30 years, and 29% (24 respondents) were aged ≥ 31 years.

customer satisfaction has a direct and significant effect on customer loyalty.

- H3: There is a significant effect of customer satisfaction on customer loyalty.

III. METHOD

The research method used is quantitative research using a structured questionnaire. This research is a hypothesis testing (Hypotheses Testing) and seen from the time period it is a cross sectional study or one shoot data collection, namely collecting information from one type of sample which is carried out only once in one period. The research sampling technique used a purposive sampling technique with the number of samples in this study being 80 (16 indicators x 5). This research uses four variables of brand image, customer experience, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The data in this study were obtained from primary sources using a questionnaire distributed online via the Google form and measured with a Likert scale. Testing the research hypothesis was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) based Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach.

IV. DISCUSSION

Primary data in this study resulted from collecting data directly from respondents through questionnaires distributed online (google form) as many as 80 respondents.

C. Description of Customer Experience Variables (X1)

Indicator Code	Distribution of Answers					Total	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Std. Deviation
	STS	TS	N	S	SS						
PP1	0	2	4	49	25	80	4,270	4	2	5	0,633
PP2	0	4	5	46	25	80	4,220	4	2	5	0,718
PP3	0	3	7	47	23	80	4,200	4	2	5	0,696
PP4	0	5	4	46	25	80	4,210	4	2	5	0,742
PP5	0	4	2	49	25	80	4,250	4	2	5	0,687
Total	0	18	22	237	123	400	4,230	20	10	25	3,478

Table 3: Analysis of Respondents' Answers to Customer Experience (X1)

Source: processing data (2022)

➤ Information :

- PP1 = Using Lazada products based on the five senses (such as: seeing or hearing Lazada products first)
- PP2 = Using Lazada products according to the customer's mood
- PP3 = Using Lazada products based on customer needs
- PP4 = Using Lazada products based on customer experience.
- PP5 = Using Lazada products based on suitability

Based on Table 3 it shows that the lowest indicator is

the PP3 indicator which states that "using Lazada products is based on customer needs" which has an average of 4,200. This can be indicated that Lazada Products are not sufficient in terms of product completeness for what customers need. While the highest indicator is found in the PP1 indicator which states that "Using Lazada products is based on the five senses. (like: seeing or hearing Lazada products first)." which has an average number of 4,270. It declares that Lazada customers use Lazada products when customers know information in advance, such as online or Lazada promotional advertisements.

D. Description of Brand Image Variable (X2)

Indicator Code	Distribution of answer					Total	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Std. Deviation
	STS	TS	N	S	SS						
CM1	1	1	2	49	27	80	4.30	4	1	5	0,6590
CM2	0	3	3	45	29	80	4.30	4	2	5	0,6741
CM3	0	9	5	44	22	80	4.090	4	2	5	0,8539
Total	1	13	10	138	78	240	4,230	12	5	15	2,1871

Table 4: Analysis of Respondents' Answers to Brand Image (X2)

Source: processing data (2022)

➤ Information:

- CM1 = Lazada products have a good reputation
- CM2 = Lazada products have benefits for customers
- CM3 = Lazada products have unique characteristics

Based on Table 4 it shows that in variable X2, the lowest indicator is the CM3 indicator which states that "products in Lazada have characteristics" which has an average number of 4,090. This can be indicated that Lazada products do not have special characteristics that distinguish them from other e-commerce products. While the highest

indicator is found in the CM1 indicator which states that "Lazada products have a good reputation." which has an average number of 4,300. This declares that Lazada customers use Lazada products because they know they have a good 'name' among their surroundings and highest indicator is the CM2 indicator which states that "Lazada products have benefits for me" which has an average of 4,300. It declares that lazada products used by customers have good effectiveness and efficiency values for customers in every activity.

E. Variable Description of Customer Satisfaction (Z)

Indicator Code	Distribution of Answer					Total	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Std. Deviation
	STS	TS	N	S	SS						
KP1	0	9	5	44	22	80	4,090	4	2	5	0,854
KP2	0	5	8	43	24	80	4,160	4	2	5	0,775
KP3	0	1	2	50	27	80	4,330	4	2	5	0,570
KP4	0	1	2	51	26	80	4,320	4	2	5	0,566
Total	0	16	17	188	99	360	4,225	16	8	20	2,765

Table 5: Analysis of Respondents' Answers to Customer Satisfaction (Z)

Source: Processed data (2022)

➤ Information:

- KP1 = Customer Buying back Lazada products
- KP2 = Customers say good things about Lazada to others
- KP3 = Customers pay little attention to other brand advertisements
- KP4 = Buying other products through Lazada

Based on Table 5 on the Z variable, the lowest

indicator is found in the KP1 indicator which states that "customers repurchase Lazada products" which has an average of 4,090. This can be indicated that Lazada's products are less attractive so that customers have less desire to buy back products on Lazada. Meanwhile, the highest indicator is found in the KP3 indicator which states that "customers do not pay attention to other brands." which has an average number of 4,330. This indicates that Lazada customers prioritize Lazada in their online shopping routine.

F. Variable Description of Customer Loyalty (Y)

Indicator code	Distribution of Answer					Total	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Std.Deviation
	STS	TS	N	S	SS						
LP1	0	4	5	46	25	80	4,220	4	2	5	0,719
LP2	0	3	7	47	23	80	4,200	4	2	5	0,696
LP3	0	0	3	43	34	80	4,410	4	3	5	0,552
LP4	1	1	2	49	27	80	4,300	4	1	5	0,659
Total	1	8	17	185	109	360	4,283	16	8	20	2,626

Table 6: Analysis of Respondents' Answers to Customer Loyalty (Y)

Source: Processed data (2022)

➤ Information:

- LP1 = Customer makes repeat purchases
- LP2 = Customer purchases between Lazada product lines
- LP3 = The customer recommends the product to others
- LP4 = Customers are not affected by products from other brands

Based on Table 6 on all Y variables, the lowest indicator is in the LP2 indicator which states that "Customers buy between Lazada product lines" which has an average of 4,200. This can be indicated that Lazada customers lack the desire to buy other Lazada products, and only buy certain products that are always purchased when shopping online at Lazada. Whereas the highest indicator is found in the LP3 indicator which states that "Customers

recommend products to others" which has an average of 4410. This indicates that Lazada customers always buy Lazada products and recommend them to others.

G. Results of Partial Least Square Analysis

The data processing technique in this study uses the SEM method based on Partial Least Square (PLS) where the data processing uses the SmartPLS 4.0 program.

H. Measurement Model Test Results (Outer Model)

The outer model consists of 3 (three) stages, namely Convergent Validity by using the correlation between indicator scores and construct scores, Discriminant Validity by comparing values in the cross loading table, and Composite Reliability values (Simamora, 2017).

I. Convergent Validity

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Specification	Information
Customer Satisfaction (Z)	KP2	0.721	>0.7	Valid
	KP3	0.922	>0.7	Valid
	KP4	0.880	>0.7	Valid
Customer Loyalty (Y)	LP1	0.745	>0.7	Valid
	LP2	0.724	>0.7	Valid
	LP3	0.766	>0.7	Valid
	LP4	0.794	>0.7	Valid
Customer Experience (X1)	PP1	0.814	>0.7	Valid
	PP2	0.797	>0.7	Valid
Customer Experience (X1)	PP3	0.765	>0.7	Valid
	PP4	0.747	>0.7	Valid
	PP5	0.851	>0.7	Valid
Brand Image (X2)	CM1	0.869	>0.7	Valid
	CM2	0.822	>0.7	Valid

Table 7: Modified Convergent Validity Test Results

Source: Processing data (2022)

Fig. 1. Results of the PLS Algorithm (Modification)

Source: SmartPLS 4 processing results (2022)

The results of the modified Convergent Validity test in Table 7 and Figure 1 show that all indicators meet Convergent Validity because they have a Loading Factor value above 0.7.

J. Discriminant Validity

Variable	Brand image	Customer satisfaction	Customer loyalty	Customer Experience
Brand image	0.848			
Customer satisfaction	0.723	0.939		
Customer loyalty	0.845	0.772	0.895	
Customer Experience	0.611	0.813	0.603	0.820

Table 8: Discriminant Validity Test Results (Fornell-Lacker Criterion)

Source: Processing data (2022)

Based on Table 8 it shows that Fornell Larcker that each variable has a larger number when compared to other variables so that the variables used are valid

K. Heterotrait Monotriat Ratio Of Correlations (HTMT)

	Brand image	Customer satisfaction	Customer loyalty	Customer Experience
Brand image				
Customer satisfaction	0.873			
Customer loyalty	0.676	0.801		
Customer Experience	0.773	0.637	0.558	

Table 9: Test Results for Heterotrait-Monotriate Ratio Of Correlations(HTMT)

Source: Processing data with SmartPLS,2022

Based on Table 9, it shows that the Heterotrait-Monotriate Ratio Of Correlations (HTMT) test shows that all HTMT values can be stated that all constructs have discriminant validity based on HTMT calculations.

L. Variance Inflating Factor (VIF)

	VIF
X1_1	2.057
X1_2	3.667
X1_3	1.692
X1_4	1.786
X1_5	4.228
X2_1	1.229
X2_2	1.228
Z2	1.422
Z3	2.913
Z4	2.420
Y1	1.418
Y2	1.300
Y3	1.664
Y4	1.748

Table 10: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test Results

Source: Processing data with SmartPLS, 2022

Based on the results from Table 4.10 regarding the results of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test, it shows that all VIF values < 10, it can be stated that all constructs are valid without multicollinearity.

M. Structural Model Test Results (Inner Model)

➤ Collinearity statistical test

	Brand image	Customer satisfaction	Customer loyalty	Customer Experience
Brand image		1.771		
Customer satisfaction			1.000	
Customer loyalty				
Customer Experience		1.771		

Table 11: Hasil Pengujian Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Source: Processing data with SmartPLS

Table 11 shows that the overall variance inflation factor (VIF) value for each indicator is < 10.00, so it can be said that the data does not have collinearity problems.

➤ Discriminant Validity Test

Indicator	Customer satisfaction (Z)	Customer loyalty (Y)	Customer Experience (X1)	Brand Image (X2)
KP2	0.747	0.606	0.664	0.406
KP3	0.922	0.742	0.717	0.623
KP4	0.880	0.724	0.765	0.728
Z1	0.638	0.792	0.747	0.451
Z2	0.746	0.841	0.765	0.416
Z3	0.662	0.766	0.518	0.644
Z4	0.638	0.794	0.552	0.669
PP1	0.737	0.737	0.814	0.591
PP2	0.638	0.638	0.797	0.451
PP3	0.746	0.746	0.779	0.416
PP4	0.562	0.562	0.797	0.670
PP5	0.681	0.681	0.851	0.524
CM1	0.603	0.638	0.552	0.869
CM2	0.721	0.555	0.567	0.822

Table 12: Discriminant Validity Test Results (Cross Loadings)

Source: Processing data (2022)

The results of Cross Loading in the Discriminant Validity analysis can be seen in table 12. It is known that each cross loading indicator for each variable is greater than the cross loading indicators of other variables. This shows

that all indicators meet discriminant validity, because they already have the highest cross-loading value in the intended construct compared to the cross-loading value in other constructs (green column).

	Specification	AVE
Customer satisfaction (Z)	>0.5	0.715
Customer loyalty(Y)	>0.5	0.574
Customer Experience(X1)	>0.5	0.633
Brand Image (X2)	>0.5	0.715

Table 13: AVE (Average Variance Extracted) test results

Source: Processing data (2022)

From Table 13 above it can be seen that the customer satisfaction variable has an AVE value (0.715), the customer loyalty variable has an AVE value (0.574), then the customer experience variable has an AVE value (0.633), and

the brand image variable has an AVE value (0.715). Thus it can be stated that each variable in this study has a good AVE value.

➤ *Composite Reliability*

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Customer satisfaction (Z)	0.821	0.883	Reliable
Customer loyalty (Y)	0.753	0.751	Reliable
Customer Experience(X1)	0.855	0.859	Reliable
Brand Image (X2)	0.846	0.883	Reliable

Table 14: Results of Testing the Validity and Reliability of the Construct

Source: Processing data (2022)

Based on the results of table 14 which explains the Composite Reliability test based on Composite Reliability and Cronbachs Alpha shows that each variable has a lift

above the minimum value of ≥ 0.7 . So that from the data that has been owned it can show that each variable in this study is reliable and can be tested for further research.

N. *Structural Model Test Results (Inner Model)*

➤ *Coefficient of Determination R-Square (R2)*

Variable	R-Square
Customer satisfaction (Z)	0.765
Customer loyalty (Y)	0.795

Table 15: R-Square Test Results

Source: Processing data (2022)

The Structural Model indicates that the model on the purchase intention variable can be said to be strong because it has a value above 0.67. Customer satisfaction produces an R-square value of 0.765 or 76.5%, meaning that customer satisfaction can be explained by creating word of mouth, focusing on one brand and making purchasing decisions at

the same company while 23.5% can be influenced by other variables not examined. . Then attitude produces an R-square value of 0.795 or 79.5% meaning that Customer Loyalty can be explained by Repetition, Referral Refers Other and Retention while 20.5% can be influenced by other variables not examined.

➤ *Coefficient of Determination f-Square (f2)*

Variable	f-square	Information
Brand Image>Customer satisfaction	0.256	Medium
Customer satisfaction >Customer Loyalty	0.892	Strong
Customer Experience >Customer satisfaction	0.685	Strong

Table 16: f-Square Test Results

Source: Processing data (2022)

The results of the F-Square test show that the relationship between Brand Image and Customer Satisfaction has a relatively medium or moderate

relationship. This is shown from the f-square value of 0.256 while other relationships have a strong value because they have values above 0.35.

➤ Predictive Relevance Value Test (Q-Square)

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Customer Loyalty	1.280.000	558.842	0.563
Customer satisfaction	600.000	372.680	0.379

Table 17: Construct Cross-Validation Redundancy Test Results

Source: Processing data (2022)

Based on table 17, the results of the construct cross-validation redundancy test show that the results of predictive relevance calculations show a Q2 value = 0.563 in the Customer Loyalty variable and a Q2 value = 0.379 in the

Customer Satisfaction variable. The calculation results show a predictive value of relevance > 0, so the model can be said to be feasible and has a relevant predictive value.

➤ Hypothesis Testing Results

No	Hypothesis	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T-Statistics	P Values	Information	Result
H1	Customer Experience - Customer satisfaction	0.685	0.148	4.620	0.000	Significant Positive	Accepted
H2	Brand Image- Customer satisfaction	0.256	0.169	1.517	0.129	Positive Not Significant	Accepted
H3	Customer satisfaction - Customer Loyalty	0.892	0.025	35.686	0.000	Significant Positive	Accepted

Table 18: Hypothesis Testing Results

Source: Processing data (2022)

O. Analysis of the variable customer experience on customer satisfaction (H1)

Based on Table 18, it shows that customers get a good experience when purchasing products at Lazada even during the Covid-19 pandemic so as to create customer satisfaction for the company. Technological developments are felt by the community, one of which is to provide convenience in shopping for anything with the technology they have. When someone gets an experience in shopping, it will give a good or bad response that can be felt by customers when using and feeling the product or service. The better the experience that is obtained by the customer, it can also increase customer satisfaction with the company. This is in line with Febriana (2014) saying that customer experience has a significant influence on consumer satisfaction and experience.

P. Variable Analysis Effect of brand image on customer satisfaction (H2)

Based on Table 18 shows, the second hypothesis (H2) which states that Brand Image has a positive but not significant effect on Customer Satisfaction, is rejected. That is, the brand image variable is not able to have a large influence on Customer Satisfaction. That with a brand image owned by a company, it is not a benchmark for customers to get satisfaction with the desired service and product. In other words, customer beliefs can vary from true attributes

based on experience to the effects of perceived selection, selective distortion, and selective retention. The results of the research conducted do not support the results of research conducted by (Setyowati, 2017), (Dennisa, et al 2016), (Sianipar, 2019), (Kurnia, 2018), and (Kurniawati, et al 2014) where Citra The brand does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction as shown by the results of the T-statistic value of 1.517, the value of the Original Sample is 0.256, the P Values are 0.129. Standard Deviation 0.169. The T-statistic value is greater than the T-table value of 1.96, the Original Sample value shows a positive value and the P Values show less than 0.05 meaning that the better the brand image that the company has, it cannot provide customer satisfaction. Therefore, it was concluded that this research occurred of course because it was influenced by the conditions faced by Lazada e-commerce during the Covid-19 pandemic, which made it difficult for Lazada to increase customer satisfaction through brand image, because of course we should understand that all other e-commerce also participate in improving the same thing.

Q. Variable Analysis of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty (H3)

Based on Table 18 shows that the third hypothesis (H3) which states that Customer Satisfaction has a positive effect on Customer Loyalty, is accepted. This research shows that the Customer Satisfaction variable is able to have a positive and significant influence on this research, which is one of the main elements in influencing Lazada Customer Loyalty during the Covid-19 pandemic. The results of the research conducted support the results of research conducted by (Viktor, 2015), (Dennisa et al 2016), (Aryani et al, 2015), and (Normasari et al 2013) where customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. A high level of customer satisfaction can certainly build and increase customer loyalty in Lazada e-commerce. When customer loyalty increases, of course the good impact will be felt by Lazada e-commerce, as well as other benefits customers will tell people around them and so on. This is a free promotional tool for the company and makes it more confident because it gets a positive response from customers.

V. CONCLUSION, LIMITATION AND IMPLICATION

A. Conclusion

The results of hypothesis testing using smartLPS 4.0 in this study show that consumer customer experience and customer satisfaction in using Lazada products have a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty. But the brand image shows that there is a positive influence but not significant. This proves that the customer experience in this study when using Lazada products has a significant role in their satisfaction in using Lazada. Customer satisfaction can either improve or increase customer loyalty, so companies need to maintain a good experience for customers and this factor becomes one of the factors that strengthen customer loyalty to these product.

B. Limitations and Implication

Based on the data analysis and research results described above, the implications of this research are theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically the results of this study contribute to the development of knowledge, insight and reference for future researchers that consumer customer experience, brand image and customer satisfaction in using Lazada products have a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty in this study, besides that it is expected to be able to do both studies, namely qualitative and quantitative to provide more in-depth research results and more effective suggestions, using variables that are not used in the pre-survey table and further research can be carried out on other e-commerce or in other business sectors, because with different objects there are likely to lead to different conclusions.

The practical implication of this research is that Lazada companies still have to pay attention to changing times, or what can be said to be "trending" so that they are not left behind in information to carry out promotions that can attract customers. Lazada must maintain the existence of its customers, so that Lazada customers can effectively recommend Lazada products to others, and companies need to maximize the quality of the products available so that they can be selected properly in order to improve the quality of the products available on the Lazada store.

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